

RestPoll

Wild pollinator survey: Questionnaire validated by the Advisory Board

WP3: ASSESSING SOCIO-ECONOMIC CO-BENEFITS, BARRIERS, AND
INCENTIVES FOR POLLINATOR RESTORATION
TASK 3.1: ASSESS THE PERCEPTION OF POTENTIAL ADOPTERS OF RESTPOLL
RESTORATION MEASURES IN CASE-STUDY AREAS

Milestone MS9

31 March 2024

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RestPoll

**Restoring Pollinator habitats across European agricultural
landscapes based on multi-actor participatory approaches**

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1. Summary

In RestPoll (Task 3.1), we are interested in analysing the perception of farmers, beekeepers, and other land users (as for example citizens) on wild pollinator benefits and measure their self-interest to restore or protect them in the case-study areas of the consortium. To this aim, we will conduct a detailed farm survey within the different case study areas to 1) identify and characterise the current status of wild pollinator restoration, by identifying how farmers perceive economic benefits (marketed and non-marketed) and risks from the restoration measures and measure the socio-economic and environmental performance of the most representative farming systems and 2) analyse the awareness of farmers towards wild pollinators and their willingness to protect them. This survey will also include beekeepers and citizens of the case-study areas where trade-offs with respect to pollinator management emerge.

This survey will be conducted within each of the case study areas (see D1.1 for more details) by a RestPoll member associated with that area as a personal interview. We will conduct 250 surveys per Living Lab. The surveys will be translated into the native language of the case study area. This includes: German, Hungarian, Spanish, Italian, Latvian, French, Danish, Greek, Ukrainian, Dutch, and Swedish. The results will be recorded by hand by the interviewers, which will later be digitized and anonymized before being uploaded to the RestPoll drive for analysis.

TIMELINE

Month 3-5 (Dec 2023 – Feb 2024): The survey was created by the authors and then reviewed by the project management.

Month 6 (Mar 2024): The survey will be reviewed by the RestPoll advisory board.

Month 8-10 (May – Jul 2024): The surveys will be tested in the Living Labs near Toulouse by N. Gallai.

Month 12-18 (Sep 2024 – Mar 2025): The surveys will be conducted in other Living Labs.

Month 19-21 (Apr – Jun 2025): Data from the surveys will be analysed.

Survey

Wild pollinator survey

Name of interviewer:

Date:

Survey location:

Time:

Hello, my name is [...] and I'm a [student or member or staff at ... University or institution ...]. Could you spare me a little of your time to answer a questionnaire about wild pollinating insects. This will take between 20 minutes for citizens and 30 minutes for farmers.

Various scientific studies have shown not knowing enough about these insects, even though they play a crucial role in pollinating agricultural crops, maintaining food diversity and preserving flower biodiversity. These same studies also show that many of these insects are in decline. It is against this backdrop that our study, conducted in partnership with the [name of the Living Labs] and the European Union, aims to gain a better understanding of how the various stakeholders in this region (farmers, elected representatives, members of associations and, more generally, local residents) perceive the role of these wild pollinators and are prepared to protect them. We are going to survey 250 people randomly per living lab in Europe. The results of our survey will be made public and presented to the general public. In particular, they are intended to inform the decision-making of local players in the field of protecting natural environments. It is in this context that we would like to hear your opinion. It will be invaluable to us. No personal data will be collected and of course, your anonymity will be guaranteed. The data will be stored on a protected hard drive and will only be used for scientific production purposes.

Part 1: Knowledge of pollinators and their environments

We will begin this questionnaire with some general questions about your relationship with the natural environment.

Question 1 Do you live in this (specify depending on the living labs) department or county?

- Yes
- No

Question 2 How would you classify this area?

- Predominantly cities area
- More of a towns and suburban area
- Predominantly rural area

Question 3 Do you think that this area is primarily (Rank the answers):

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Description of the area	Rank (from 1 to 4 or 5; 1 being the best)
A recreational area (a place for relaxation and leisure)	
An economically developed area (for example through the development of tourism or agriculture)	
A protected natural area	
A space representative of the region's cultural heritage	
Other: _____	

Question 4 How well would you say you know the following groups of plants and animals in your local area:

Plants and animals	"I don't know anything about this group"	"I can identify a few common species"	"I know a lot of different species"
Crops			
Flowering plants			
Trees			
Insects			
Birds			
Mammals			
Mushrooms			
Other			

Question 5 Do you know what a pollinator is?

- Yes
 I think so
 I think not
 No
 If it is positive (i.e. "yes" or "I think so"), could you describe?

Question 6 Did you know that insects can be pollinators?

- Yes
- No

Question 7 On the following poster, could you tell me which pollinators you recognize?

[Poster pollinators (pg. 1 of [powerpoint](#))]

Question 8 On the following poster, do you know what natural places wild pollinators live in?

- Yes
- I think so
- I am not sure
- No

[Poster habitats (pg. 2 of [powerpoint](#))]

Question 9 If so, still based on the poster, are you able to tell me where these pollinators live?

Question 10 Could you rank the different roles of wild pollinators depending on the importance you give to each of the services they offer? (from most important to least important)?

The services provided by wild pollinators are beneficial because...	Rank (from 1 to 11; 1 being the best)
they exist, and it makes me happy to know that they exist (pollinator species in their own right).	
they are a web of life support (Wider ecological values of pollinators in ecosystems, faunistic and floristic biodiversity)	
they will pass on all their profits to future generations (responsibility to future generations)	
they are a biodiversity flagship (Pollinators are important to research and education in e.g. ecology, biology)	
they participate to leisure and recreation (Pollination contributes to leisure and recreational activities such as butterfly recording, pollinator friendly gardening, etc)	
they participate to aesthetic (Pollinators contribute to a flower-rich landscapes, to the public and home gardens)	
they participate to art (Pollinators inspire artists (e.g. movies, paintings, etc.)	
they provide varieties of food (The production of certain fruit and vegetables depends on pollination by pollinators (zucchini, strawberries, etc.) contrary to others (lettuce) (Klein et al., 2007). The degradation of pollinators can change the offering of EU grown fruits and vegetables in market stands.)	
they provide nutritional quality and healthy food (Pollinator-dependent crops contribute up to 40% of the world's supply of nutrients and around 90% of Vitamin C in crops is produced thanks to insect pollination (Ellis et al. 2015; Eilers et al. 2011).)	
they guarantee amount and stability of yield (Insect pollination benefits agricultural yields (about 8 to 10 % of the value of global edible crop production depends on pollinators; Lautenbach et al., 2012))	
they provide seed production (Pollination impacts on seed production)	

I don't know

We've just finished with the general part. We're now going to ask you some more specific questions about your relationship with the natural environment, and more particularly with the pollinating insects it shelters.

Part 2: Your perception of wild and other pollinators

Question 11 How many (if any) honey bee hives do you own?

Question 12 Are you a member of any organizations...

- ...that encourage environmental conservation
- ...that represent beekeepers
- ...that represent farmers and other land owners
- ...No

Question 13 Do you usually (from April to August) grow fruit and/or vegetables at home or in a shared garden?

- Yes, at home
- Yes, at a shared garden
- No, I do not grow fruit and vegetables → 17
- Other: _____

If so, which ones? _____

Question 14 Why do you grow fruit and vegetables? (Several answers are possible)

- For pleasure
- Because the fruit and vegetables I grow are good quality and tasty
- Because I can plant what I want
- As a matter of principle
- Because it's good for your health
- Because I know what products (fertilizers, plant protection products) I'm using.
- Because it's a way for me to reconnect with the land
- Because my parents did it, it's traditional
- Because it saves me money
- Other:

Question 15 Do you usually buy local (less than 100km than home) fruit and vegetables between April and August?

More than once a week Once a week Once every fortnight Less than once a month Never I don't know

What are the main local fruits and vegetables you buy?

Question 16 Why do you buy local fruit and vegetables? (Several answers are possible)

- Because the prices are attractive
- Because the products are of high quality and tasty
- Because the products are attractive, well-shaped, etc.
- Because the products on offer are very varied
- On principle
- Because it's good for your health
- Because it helps preserve the natural environment
- Because it supports the local economy
- Other:

Question 17 Do you frequently visit natural areas such as green spaces, forests or woods and the surrounding nature parks?

More than once a week Once a week Once every fortnight Less than once a month Never I don't know

Why?

Question 18 Could you tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with each of these 4 statements? To answer, use a scale from 1 to 4. You will answer 1 if you strongly disagree with the statement and 4 if you strongly agree with the statement.

	Strongly disagree Strongly agree	I have no idea
In the region's natural areas, you can appreciate the abundance of flowers present		
In the region's natural spaces, you can appreciate the diversity (the fact of many different types of) of flowers present		
The current state of the flowers and flora in the region's natural areas gives you cause for concern.		
You are concerned about the future state of the flowers and flora in the region's natural areas.		

Question 19 Have you noticed any changes in the surrounding landscape in recent years?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If so, which one(s)?

Question 20 Is leaving the environment in a better condition than it is at present for future generations a key concern for you?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Question 21 Would you want to leave this environment to future generations in its current state?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If not, why?

Question 22 Did you know that the population of wild pollinating insects is highly dependent on the health of the natural environment and landscapes?

- Yes
- I think so
- Not sure
- No

If so, how did you get this information?

- Social media
- Internet
- Training
- Education
- Observation
- Other:-----

Question 23 Did you know that some wild pollinators are in decline?

- Yes
- I think so
- I think not
- No

If so, how did you get this information?

- Social media
- Internet
- Training
- Education
- Observation
- Other:-----

Question 24 Do you think we can compensate for this decline by making greater use of domestic managed pollinators, such as honeybees kept in hives?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

[Providing knowledge in order to ensure that all participants answer the questionnaire with at least the same basic level.]

Pollinating insects in general, and wild ones in particular, are in decline around the world. We are here to understand the consequences of this decline for our society. That's why, in the next stage, we're going to present you with different scenarios showing several possible changes in the state of the natural environment. We're going to ask you to compare these different scenarios and choose the one you prefer.

Part 3: Choice cards (please see Table on page 21)

For each option, the following question will be asked:

Question 25 On a scale from 0 to 10, how certain are you of the scenario you have chosen? In other words, how convinced are you of your choice and are confident you would make this choice if asked again?

0 corresponding to absolutely uncertain and 10 to absolutely certain

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Option number	Which scenario would you choose?				Degree of certainty (between 0 and 10)	You have ticked one additional payment per year equal to €0. Why did you make this choice?
	I don't know	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3		
Option	I don't know	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3		
Option	I don't know	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3		
Option	I don't know	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3		
Option	I don't know	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3		
Option	I don't know	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3		

In all your choices, do you consider that you have taken into account all the elements on the choice cards? Let me remind you of these elements: the quantity and variety of fruit and vegetables available on local markets, the diversity of wild flowers, the proportion of species of wild pollinators that have disappeared, the time it takes for the benefits of a scenario to appear.

- Yes
- No

Question 26 If not, which ones have you omitted?

- Variety and quantity of fruit and vegetables available at local markets
- Wildflower diversity
- Proportion of wild pollinator species available
- Time of occurrence of the scenario
- Volunteer working time
- Type of payment

I would now like to ask you a few questions about the actions you think would be most appropriate to protect the natural environment and the wild pollinating insects it shelters.

Part 4: Action to be taken

Question 27 Which of the following aerial views of the landscape do you prefer?

Aerial view A

Aerial view B

Aerial view C

None I don't know

Landscape A

Landscape B

Landscape C

Explain why you prefer this Landscape:

- Growing crops
- Recreation
- Esthetic
- Others: _____

Question 28 Which of these aerial views do you think is most conducive to maintaining or developing wild pollinators?

Aerial view A

Aerial view B

Aerial view C

None I don't know

Question 29 Could you tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with each of these 3 statements?

To answer, use a scale from 1 to 4. You will answer 1 if you strongly disagree with the statement and 4 if you strongly agree with the statement.

	Strongly disagree Strongly agree	I have no idea
It is important for you to protect the natural environment.		
It is important for you to take action against the decline in wild pollinators.		
Protection of the environment and wild pollinators is important to the public		

Question 30 Do you think that an environmental tax on revenue can help protect wild pollinators?

- Yes
- No

Question 31 Do you think that volunteering with environmental associations can help protect wild pollinators?

- "Yes, and I would be prepared and able to give up some of my time to participate"
- "Yes, but I would not be prepared or able to give up my time to participate"
- "No, I do not think these associations can help protect wild pollinators"

Question 32 Would you be prepared to get personally involved in protecting wild pollinators?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Question 33 If so, how?

- By making a financial contribution (contribution to the funding of an association involved in the preservation of wild pollinators, etc.)
- By contributing my expertise and knowledge (I'm a beekeeper, farmer and I've studied ecology, etc.)
- By providing voluntary help (membership of an association for the protection of wild pollinating insects, involvement in the field, etc.)
- By changing my daily practices (using fewer chemicals, respecting the natural habitats of pollinating insects, etc.)
- Buying pollinator-friendly products
- Other: _____

Question 34 Select three measures do you think would be most effective in protecting wild pollinators?

Measures	
• Integrate the protection of wild pollinators into the management of green spaces by local authorities.	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Encourage residents to plant pollinator-friendly flowers and set up insect hotels in their gardens.	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Reduce the use of chemical products: pesticides, fungicides, insecticides and herbicides.	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Controlling urban development and encouraging grouped housing.	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Conserve and develop natural habitats for wild pollinating insects: meadows, hedgerows, flower fallow, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Installing beehives taking into account the habitats of wild pollinators. This means not placing beehives too close to the natural habitats of wild pollinators so as not to create too much competition and put additional pressure on wild pollinators.	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Encouraging a change in farming practices, with greater crop diversification.	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Other (clarify):	<input type="checkbox"/>

Only for professional farmers

Question 35 How big is your farm?

- less than 10 ha
- 10 - 25 ha
- 25 - 50 ha
- 50 - 100 ha
- 100 - 200 ha
- More than 200 ha

Question 36 What is the farm's main activity?

- Dairy cattle
- Beef cattle
- Mixed cattle
- Tree crops
- Arable crops
- Horticulture, market gardening
- Sheep, other cattle feeding exclusively on plants.
- Multi-crop livestock farming
- Pigs, poultry
- Viticulture

Question 37 What variety or crop or breed of animals do you most often use?

Question 38 Are any of your products labelled? [y / n]

If so, under which label(s) are your products marketed?

- AOC/AOP
- PGI
- Label Rouge
- Traditional Speciality Guaranteed (TSG)
- Organic Farming
- Nature et Progrès
- Ecocert
- LEAF

Question 39 What is the main way you market your products?

- "direct to consumers"
- "direct to retailers"
- "to wholesalers or marketing boards"
- Long distribution chain

Question 40 Could you tell us:

- Your approximate average annual turnover in euros per year over the last 4 years:
- Your average production cost in euros per year over the last 4 years:

Question 41 On your farm, have you contracted an Agro-environmental Scheme (AES)?

- Yes
- No

If yes, which one?

Question 42 Approximately how much does it cost you per hectare to implement the environmental practices associated with the Agro-Environmental Scheme (AES) contract?

Question 43 Of the types of practices listed in the table below, can you tell me which ones you actually use?

Question 44 How do you think this AES has impacted wild pollinating insects on your farm and the surrounding landscape, or in the region/country in general?

- Positive
- Negative
- None
- I don't know

If so, in what way?

Question 45 Please tell me which ones you think have a positive, negative or no impact on:

- a. Increasing the total number of pollinators in my farm/the local the landscape
- b. Encouraging different types of pollinators in my farm/the local landscape

If so, can you give us more details?

Types of farming practices	Practices actually implemented:	a - Increasing the total number of pollinators in my farm/the local the landscape	b - Encouraging more different types of pollinators in my farm/the local landscape	c- has no effect	Explain the impact
Crop rotation (Diversification)	Number of crops grown on the farm? Are they combined?				
Rotation	Crop rotation: Yes/No Over how many years is the rotation planned?				
Managing plant protection products	Use of plant protection products: Yes/No Quantity used per year and per hectare by type of product				
Maintaining agro-ecological infrastructure (e.g. the alignments of trees and their grass strips on the edge or in plots, forest edges, hedges, banks, low walls, ditch borders, streams ...; or maintaining wet meadows, orchards, rangelands, wastelands, groves, wetlands ...; or preserving ponds, springs, isolated trees, rocks)	Are there any agro-environmental infrastructures on your farm? Yes/No If yes, explain which one and Approximately what proportion of your UAA (Utilised Agricultural Area) does this infrastructure represent?				
Soil preparation	What type of tillage do you use? Ploughing/semi-tillage/shallow tillage/0 ploughing				
Chemical fertiliser	What type of fertiliser do you use? Mineral fertilisation/Organic fertilisation/Both. If you use chemical fertilisation, what quantities are applied per year?				
Habitat creation/restoration	Flower margins, patches, low input meadows, set aside, scrub, riparian buffer strips etc.				
Habitat management/maintenance	Flower margins, patches, low input meadows, set aside, scrub, riparian buffer strips etc.				

The maintenance and/or management of the existing habitats, in connecting with the habitat creation/restoration	Flower margins, patches, low input meadows, set aside, scrub, riparian buffer strips etc.				
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Question 46 If you use at least one of the agri-environmental practices mentioned above (crop rotation, crop rotation plan, reduction of inputs, simplification of tillage, etc.), could you rank the main reasons why?

Agri-environmental practices	Rank (from 1 to 4 or 5; 1 being the best)
Agronomic (improving soil fertility, combating erosion, etc.)	
Economic (reduced input costs and gains from subsidies, etc.)	
Environmental (helping to preserve the natural environment)	
Professional (greater decision-making autonomy, improved image of my profession, etc.)	
Other: _____	

I have no idea

Question 47 If you do not use any of the agri-environmental practices mentioned above (crop rotation, crop rotation plan, reduction of inputs, simplification of tillage, etc.), could you tell the main reasons why?

Reason of not using agri-environmental practices	Rank (from 1 to 6 or 7; 1 being the best)
Lack of time	
Financial cost	
Risk of crop loss and product quality	
Lack of knowledge, training and technical support	
Administrative constraints	
Close to retirement	
Other: _____	

Question 48 What conditions would be required for you to adopt these practices?

Question 49 Does your farm have any innovative or unusual practices in general? If so, what are these practices?

I'd like to end this interview by asking you a few more personal questions. Of course, your anonymity will be guaranteed. The information gathered will be used primarily to process our data and analyse our results. I would like to remind you that we are surveying 250 people in this area.

Part 5: Personal information

Question 50 Gender

- Man
- Woman
- Transgender man
- Transgender woman
- Cis man
- Cis woman
- Non-binary
- Other
- I prefer not to disclose

Question 51 How old are you?

16 to 29 years 30 to 44 years 45 to 59 years 60 to 74 years 75 years and over

Question 52 What is your personal situation?

- Single
- In a relationship
- In a civil partnership
- Married
- I prefer not to disclose

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Other: _____

Question 53 How many people (yourself included) live in your household?

Question 54 How many dependent children do you have?

Question 55 What sector do you work in?

- Agriculture and agri-food
- Industry and energy
- Services (trade, tourism, insurance, banking, etc.)
- Other: _____

Question 56 What do you do for a living?

- Farmer
- Beekeeper
- Craftsmen / women
- Shopkeepers and related occupations
- Heads of companies with more than 10 employees
- Liberal professions
- Administrative and technical civil servants
- Professors and higher scientific occupations
- Information, arts and entertainment professionals
- Managers in administrative and commercial services
- Engineers and technical managers
- Professions in primary and vocational education, continuing education and sport
- Occupations in health and social work
- Ministers of Religion and Consecrated Religious
- Occupations in the public service (administration, security)
- Administrative and commercial occupations in companies
- Technicians
- Supervisors (excluding administrative supervisors)
- Public service administrative employees, service agents and health auxiliaries
- Police officers, military personnel, firefighters, private security guards
- Administrative clerks
- Commercial clerks
- Employees in direct services to individuals
- Skilled industrial workers
- Skilled craft workers
- Transport vehicle drivers, delivery drivers, couriers

- Equipment Operators, Forklift Drivers, Storekeepers and Transport Workers (non-road)
- Agricultural, forestry, fishing and aquaculture worker
- Other worker
- Retired
- Predominantly parental care, or other care
- Looking for work
- I don't want to respond

Question 57 Place of residence:

Do you live in this area all year round? Or are you here only part of the year?

Permanent resident OR Second home

City: _____ Municipality : _____

Question 58 Where did you spend most of your childhood (from 0 to 16)?

- In a major city, in the city center
- In a suburb or on the outskirts of town
- In a rural area

Question 59 What is your level of education?

- BAC (Highschool) + 5 years and more
- BAC (Highschool) + 3 years or more
- BAC (Highschool), BTS, DUT or equivalent
- BAC (Highschool) level or lower

Question 60 What is your total net annual income?

Less than €9000	10.000 to 18 000€	19 000€ to 28 000€	29 000€ to 40 000€	41 000€ to 55 000€	Higher than 56 000€
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Question 61 If you are a couple, what is your partner's total net annual income?

Less than €9000	10.000 to 18 000€	19 000€ to 28 000€	29 000€ to 40 000€	41 000€ to 55 000€	Higher than 56 000€
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We are coming to the end of our survey. Thank you very much for your participation.

Question 62 Would you like to be informed of the results of this survey?

- Yes, I am interested. Contact (Email, Tel):

- No, I am not

Question 63 Do you have any other information to share with us? Any other comments you would like to make?

Focus Groups

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

I would also like to inform you that in order to complete the study, we have scheduled meetings for groups of 6 to 10 people. These meetings will take place from the beginning of June. Each meeting will last approximately one hour. The aim is to get local stakeholders to discuss the issue of wild pollinators and the local measures that can be taken to protect them more effectively. At the end of each meeting, we will be offering a small snack so that participants can continue their discussions in a convivial atmosphere.

Question 64 Would you be prepared to take part in one of these meetings?

- Yes, I am interested

Phone number: _____

eMail: _____

- No, I am not

Table of Attribute and levels for the choice modeling approach

These attributes and levels will be used to produce the multiple scenarios proposed to participants of the survey.

Attribute	Description	Levels	Value of Levels
Food production	The impact of pollination on food production in term of quality and quantity	High Low	100% 50%
Diversity of wild flora	The impact of pollination on wild flora production	High Low	100% 70%
Existence value of wild pollinator	The value people give to the existence of wild pollinators. This value is the marginal utility gain by knowing that these insects exist	High Low	1 0
Time scale	The moment when the scenario happens.	In a long time In a short time	5 years 1 year
Volunteer time	Volunteer time (hour) per month I'm prepared to devote per week to an environmental association to protect wild pollinating insects.	High Medium Low	6 hours 4 hours 2 hours 0 hour
Payment amount	The tax I am willing to pay per year for the preservation of wild pollinators	High Medium Low null	15 euros 10 euros 5 euros 0 euro**

**As the survey will be address in many countries, we could adapt the payment dependently of a percentage of the minimum salary: 0%, 0,005%, 0,010%, 0,015%.